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**SCHOOL ADMINISTRATORS' APPROACHES FOR ENHANCING IMPLEMENTATION OF
CURRICULUM IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ABAKILIKI EDUCATIONAL ZONE, EBONYI
STATE**

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ABSTRACT

This research work centered on school Administrators' approaches for enhancing implementation of curriculum in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi State. One research question and one null hypothesis guided the study. A descriptive survey research design with random sampling techniques was used. The population of the study was made up of all the 3220 teachers and the 110 principals of the public secondary schools in the Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state, making a total of 3330 respondents. A sample size of 357 respondents was used, using Taro-Yamane's formular to draw from the population across the education zone. Instrument for data collection was a researcher-made questionnaire duly validated and the reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach alpha, which yielded a co-efficient index of 0.83. The researcher and 5 research assistants administered and retrieved the questionnaire; with 98.3% return rate. Mean and standard deviations were used to answer the research questions while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The analyzed data identified school principal approaches, such as regular orientation of new students on goals and objectives of the subject matters and retraining of teachers by the government in order to be conversant with the basic skills required for effective teaching. The study recommended among others that government should at all times provide qualified teachers, adequate facilities and equipment for effective teaching and learning.

Keywords: School Administrators, Curriculum, Approaches, Implementation, Secondary Schools

INTRODUCTION

Every government in the world works to ensure that its citizens receive an education because they recognize how important it is for social stability as well as economic prosperity (REPOA, 2008). Education is supposed to generate graduates who can meet challenges, solve issues, be critical and active citizens, be entrepreneurial and create jobs, and flourish in a fast-paced, complex environment (TEN/MET, 2008). Through the introduction of pre-vocational and vocational electives, respectively, Nigeria, like many other nations, has drastically improved the quality of education, especially in terms of classroom facilities and enrolment (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013). In enumeration, UNESCO (2011) points out that the rapid expansion of students enrolments, led to inadequate resources which resulted into difficulties in creating expected outcomes. However, achievement in students' academic performance in community secondary schools cannot be achieved if school heads are not in fully committed to play their roles effectively.

Curriculum on the other hand is defined as a planned and guided learning experience and intended learning outcome formulated through systematic reconstruction of knowledge and experience under the auspices of the school, for the learners continuous and willful growth in personal and social competence. According to Hornby (2010), curriculum refers to the disciplines that are taught in schools, colleges, and other educational institutions. According to these definitions of curriculum, the curriculum needs to be executed well in order to guarantee that students continuously and consciously develop their social and personal competency. Curriculum implementation is the task of translating the curriculum document into the operating curriculum by the combined efforts of the student, teachers, school principals and the government at large. The relevance of a curriculum can only be determined if it is implemented effectively in the classroom. However, the Principal as the administrative head who is accountable to the Schools Management ensures the effective and efficient utilization of human and material resources towards the achievement of educational goals. Reiterating on the position of the school principal, Muring (2014) posited that the much more, the duties and responsibilities of principals expanded further to include the responsibility for leading school reform that would raise student achievement through adequate utilization of organizational elements. Some of these elements are clear statements of aims and objectives, hierarchy of authority, unity of command, delegation of authority, division of labour, and effective communication and coordination of various tasks such as staff development and students' personnel functions.

The principal is often in charge of organising the activities at the secondary school. To supervise the correct operation of the school in terms of staff and student welfare and discipline, the principal is chosen based on seniority and qualifications. According to Oyewale and Alonge (2013), the principal of the school system serves as both a supervisor and a professional leader, combining the responsibilities of subject supervisors, instructional supervisors, and administrative supervisors. The administrative efficacy and efficiency of the principal and the government in carrying out the aforementioned curriculum are critical to the growth and development of secondary schools in Nigeria; hence the overall objective of the revised curriculum is to provide students with adequate knowledge and skills that will enable them to discover their talents and enrich education in Nigeria (NERDC, 2012). Substantially, the objectives and goals of educational programmes at the secondary school levels in Ebonyi state and Nigeria at large as enunciated in the curriculum have not being fully realized and this may be attributed to numerous factors such as lack of the effective teachers of the subject, shortage of facilities and teaching materials, poor attitudes of the students, use of inappropriate teaching techniques, poor supervision of the teachers by the principals and use of unqualified teachers and teachers with obsolete ideas as well as ineffectiveness of the teachers (Vera Rosemary & Bashir, 2016). The teacher is someone who is trained academically to impart knowledge, skills and values to the learner. Thus, as Egwin (2017) stated, "teachers should implement whatever innovations, to be made in the education of any nation." Therefore, the curriculum's failure would eventually result from the failure of the teachers and other staff in the school system, which serves as the pivot for the implementation of the educational curriculum. Teachers and other necessary staff should receive proper training, incentives, sufficient teaching materials, supervision, and appropriate teaching methods to ensure that curriculum are implemented effectively. Furthermore, Muring (2014) noted that while there are many certified teachers, there aren't many who are actually qualified to teach kids things. Olaitan and Mama (2014) noted that teachers' professional training, experience and interest are supposed to help greatly in achieving progress towards the different subjects in secondary schools, but in this era, it has not been so. The technique and curricula of education at all levels have also seen significant changes since Nigeria gained its independence in 1960 (Egwin, 2017), but regrettably, the general public has believed that the quality

of education has been declining. It is clear from all signs that achieving the quality of education in Nigeria requires a thorough examination of strategies for enhancing curriculum implementation.

In the context of this study, to improve the curriculum's effective implementation means to raise, intensify, or improve the teachers' value, quality, and degree of performance in order to attain a desired outcome in their instruction as well as the students' performance on internal and external exams. If teachers and other school system employees are not properly positioned and cared for to teach effectively, students will not gain the necessary skills, which will have a negative impact on the nation's development and the accomplishment of curriculums' objectives. This study sought to understand how school administrators in the Abakiliki Educational Zone of Ebonyi State, Nigeria, could improve the implementation of curriculum in secondary schools.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Among other things, the goals of teaching and learning in line with the secondary school curriculum in Nigeria among others is to show that education is a worthwhile endeavor because it helps them learn more about fundamental life principles and practices, develop their understanding of societal values, and support environmental conservation initiatives. Despite the significance, there is proof that few students enrol and graduate successfully, and this can be linked to both institutional and non-institutional-based issues.

Operationally, it has been noted that a shortage of funding impeded facility expansion, resulting in particular issues with the implementation of various subjects. In light of this, the purpose of this study was to determine school Administrators' approaches for enhancing implementation of curriculum in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi State, Nigeria.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of the study was centered on school administrators' approaches for enhancing implementation of curriculum in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi State., Nigeria.

RESEARCH QUESTION

What are the school principal approaches necessary for enhancing effective implementation of curriculum in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi State?

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

This null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance:

HO₁: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of teachers and the principals on the school principal approaches necessary for enhancing effective implementation of curriculum in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Review framework

Murphy's Framework of Instructional Leadership (1985) served as the foundation for this study: Four fundamental aspects of instructional leadership were established by Murphy (1990): establishing a mission and goals; overseeing the programmes; encouraging high-quality instruction and tracking student achievement; and fostering a supportive school

climate. Murphy expanded the idea of encouraging a pleasant school climate with a distinct focus on improving a supportive work environment, even if creating a school's mission is one of the core components of this framework. Murphy's model (1990) established the necessity of instructional leadership independent of the organizational structure of the school. He determined that principals are in charge of five key areas: establishing the school's mission; overseeing curriculum and instruction; encouraging a supportive learning environment; monitoring and enhancing instruction; and evaluating the educational programme. The importance of instructional leaders in overseeing curriculum, particularly curriculum revisions, is emphasised by these two approaches. Effective change management is expected as most educational adjustments are made with the goal of enhancing current procedures and frameworks.

The framework help principals envision, organise, and oversee curricular modifications. Theoretically, individual acts during the unfreezing phase of transformation are based on cultural factors and past learning. Unfreezing is the process of introducing fresh concepts and methods into a school to replace outdated ones. Examining how principals are ready for these changes by abandoning traditional curriculum approaches and concentrating on new ones is pertinent to the education system's curriculum reforms.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive survey research design and it was considered suitable because the opinion of a representative sample of respondents was sought using questionnaire and the finding was generalized on the entire population. The population of the study was made up of all the 3220 teachers and the 110 principals of the public secondary schools in the Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi state, making a total of 3330 respondents. A sample size of 357 respondents was used, using Taro-Yamane's formula to draw from the population across the education zone. The instrument for data collection was questionnaire titled: School Administrators' Approaches for Enhancing Implementation of Curriculum Questionnaire (SAAEICQ). The questionnaire was developed from literature by the researchers and used for data collection. The instrument was a four point response scale of strongly agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly disagreed (SD) with corresponding values of 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. The instrument was face – validated by three experts: Two from Department of Science Education- Alex Ekwueme Federal University, Ndufu-Alike Ikwo, Ebonyi State and one from Measurement and Evaluation Department- Ebonyi state University. Their corrections and suggestions were utilized to improve the initial copies of the questionnaire to produce the final copies. Cronbach Alpha reliability method was adopted to determine the internal consistency of the questionnaire items. A Cronbach Alpha coefficient of 0.83 was obtained and the collected data was analyzed using mean for research questions and t-test was used for the test of hypothesis. Any mean response of 2.50 and above was considered agreed while any mean response below 2.50 was considered disagreed. For hypothesis testing, t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis for any item was rejected when the calculated p -value is less than the alpha value of 0.05 but is accepted when the p -value is greater than the alpha value of 0.05.

RESULTS

Research Question 1

What are the school principal approaches necessary for enhancing effective implementation of curriculum in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi State?

Data for answering research question 1 are presented in Table 1

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on School Principal Approaches Necessary for Enhancing Effective Implementation of Curriculum in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi State (n=357)

S/N	School principal approaches	\bar{X}	SD	Rmk
1	Provision of funds to the teachers to procure resources for teaching and learning	3.22	.68	Agreed
2	Establishing small scale farms at the school for students practical Agriculture	3.40	.64	Agreed
3	Principal of schools should see the students often to know their challenges as part of his administrative duties	3.40	.64	Agreed
4	Giving awards to best subject students	3.31	.73	Agreed
5	Adopting demonstration techniques in teaching by teachers	3.26	.68	Agreed
6	Regular orientation of new students on goals and objectives of their education programmes	3.26	.68	Agreed
7	Motivate students by citing examples of job opportunities that await them after graduation	3.24	.76	Agreed
8	Re-raining of teachers on how to source and improve instructional material.	3.22	.75	Agreed
9	Allowing students to participate actively in the practical class to enable the articulate their views for asking and answering questions	3.31	.73	Agreed
10	Use of qualified teachers with better understanding of tools and equipment should be use for practical class	3.21	.77	Agreed
11	Adopting relevant instructional materials common in the immediate environment during practical work	3.26	.68	Agreed
12	Training of teachers on the use of internet to assess information.	3.22	.75	Agreed
13	Regular evaluation of students by teachers in other to accesses the strength and weakness of the curriculum	3.31	.73	Agreed

SD = Standard Deviation of the respondents and \bar{X} = Mean of the respondents

Data in Table 1 revealed that all the 13 items had their mean ratings ranging from 3.21 to 3.40 and were above the cut-off point of 2.50. This indicated that the respondents agreed on all the identified school principal approaches necessary for enhancing effective implementation of curriculum programmes in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi State, Nigeria. The standard deviation of the 13 items ranged from .64 to .77, which showed that the respondents were not too far from the mean and opinion of one another in their responses on the school principal approaches necessary for enhancing effective implementation of curriculum in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi State.

Test of Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of teachers and the principals on the school principal approaches necessary for enhancing effective implementation of curriculum in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi State.

Table 2: t-test analysis of mean difference between teachers and the principals on the school principal approaches necessary for enhancing effective implementation of curriculum in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi State.

	N	X	SD	Df	t-cal	α	Sig.	Decision
Teachers	251	3.31	.61	355	0.738	0.05	.46	Accepted H ₀₁
Principal	106	3.26	.52					

Source: t-test Result from SPSS

Data on table 2 shows that the *p*-value of .46 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, which indicates that the hypothesis stated is accepted. Which means there is no significant difference between the mean responses of teachers and the principals on the school principal approaches necessary for enhancing effective implementation of curriculum in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings were discussed based on the following sub-heading derived from the study objectives and research questions: school principal approaches necessary for enhancing effective implementation of curriculum in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi State.

The responses of principal and teachers on school principal approaches necessary for enhancing effective implementation of curriculum in secondary schools, the result revealed that all that the 13 items had their mean ratings ranging from 3.21 to 3.40 and were above the cut-off point of 2.50. This indicated that the respondents agreed on all the identified school principal approaches necessary for enhancing effective implementation of curriculum in secondary schools in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi State, Nigeria. The standard deviation of the 13 items ranged from .64 to .77, which showed that the respondents were not too far from the mean and opinion of one another in their responses on the school principal approaches necessary for enhancing effective implementation of curriculum in secondary schools. However, the findings of the above study were in agreement with the view of Offormam (2011) who revealed that school supervision, effective school communication, adequate funds to the teachers to procure implementation resources and human support are among the principal’s significant contributions towards ensuring effective teaching and learning implementation. More so, the views and observations of the authors cited on the school principal approaches necessary for enhancing effective implementation of curriculum in secondary schools helped to justify the findings of the study on research question 1.

CONCLUSION

The study's findings showed that secondary school curriculum will be implemented more effectively if the identified school principal approaches and governmental approaches required for improving the effective implementation of curriculum in secondary schools in Abakiliki Educational Zone, Ebonyi State, are sufficiently taken into consideration.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations were made;

1. There should be adequate budget allocation to fund teaching and learning in secondary schools in the country
2. There should be adequate provision of scholarship to outstanding performing students in different subjects

3. The ministry of education in collaboration with the secondary school principals should provide adequate incentives to the teachers so that they will do their work well. Such incentives as free medical services, hazard allowances and free house accommodation
4. The ministry of education of should always organize re-training programmes in the form of conferences, workshops and seminars to update the teacher's knowledge in the pedagogical techniques in teaching.
5. Only qualified teachers should be engaged in teaching and learning in secondary schools in the country.

REFERENCES

- Burnes, B. (2019). The origins of Lewin's three-step model of change. *The Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 56(1), 32–59.
- Egwin, G.A. (2017). New Federal Education Policy Lacks Fundamentals. *Nigeria Statesman*. October 8, p.12
- Federal Ministry of Education (FME) (2013). National Curriculum for Senior Secondary Schools, Ibadan: Heinemann Educational books (Nig) Ltd.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2012). National Policy On Education. Lagos: NERDC Press.
- Hornby, A. S. (2010). *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary of Current English*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Jones, M.R. (2010). Nebraska symposium on motivation. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 3(2), 295-302.
- Murphy, J. (1990). Principal instructional leadership. In LS Lotto & PW Thurston (eds). *Advances in educational administration: Changing perspectives on the school* (Vol. 1). Greenwich, CT: JAI Press.
- Muring, J. V. (2014). Managok Elementary School, Malaybalay City East District, The Challenging Roles of a School Principal, April 21, 2014.
- Nieuwenhuis F.J & Mokoena S. P. (2001). *Management of educational institutions: Module A*. Florida: TSA.
- Offorma, D. (2011). A critical appraisal of Mode of implementation of Nigeria secondary school curriculum: towards socio-economic empowerment of youth (published research work).
- Olaitan, S. O. & Mama, R. O. (2014). *Principles and practice of school farm management*. Owerri: Cape Publishers Int'l Ltd.
- Onuekwusi, G. C. & Okorie, L. (2008). Attitude of secondary school students in Abia State towards career in Agriculture. *Agricultural Journal*, 2008: 3 (2), 102-106.
- Oyewale, B. K., & Alonge, H. O. (2013). Principals' instructional supervisory role performance and teachers' motivation in Ekiti Central Senatorial District of Ekiti State, Nigeria.
- REPOA (2018). The impact of reforms on the quality of primary education in Tanzania, research report Dar es Salaam: E&D vision publishing Ltd.
- TEN/MET (2008). Strengthening education in Tanzania, Dar Es Salaam: UNICEF.
- UNESCO-IICBA (2011). Better Schools: Resource Materials for School head in Africa (Introductory Module A- User's guide. Unit One). Retrieved from
- Vera Rosemary, A. and Bashir, A. M. (2016), The Role of Effective Supervision on Academic Performance of Senior High Schools in Ghana. *Journal of Arts & Humanities*, 5(4), 73 – 83.